

Why Hunter L and a/b Move in Opposite Directions in Tomato Paste: A Review and a New Colour Score.

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ABSTRACT

A clear negative association between Hunter L (lightness) and the a/b redness ratio is frequently observed in tomato paste at production time. This review assembles mechanistic and process-level explanations for that pattern, focusing on hot-break versus cold-break processing, evaporation (vacuum vs atmospheric), and measurement practice on the Hunter Lab scale. Fundamentally, higher concentrations of red carotenoids (principally lycopene) raise a and thus a/b while reducing reflectance (lowering L). Thermal severity during breaking and concentration further darkens the matrix (Maillard browning) and can degrade or isomerise lycopene, often depressing a/b when heat load is excessive. During the 2021–2025 tomato seasons, a new composite index called Process Score (PS) was developed and validated to complement traditional Hunter Lab colour metrics (L, a, b and a/b). PS integrates redness (a), yellowness (b), and darkness (L), weighted by the CIE-x chromatic coordinate, aiming to better capture the effects of thermal processing and pigment retention. Finally, practical aspects of HunterLab measurement—tile hitching, dilution/optical path control, and sample presentation—modulate L and a/b in systematic ways.

Keywords: Hunter Lab colour (L, a, b; a/b), lycopene, hot break, cold break, vacuum evaporation, Maillard browning, sample presentation, tomato color score.

INTRODUCTION

Processed tomato colour is routinely measured on the Hunter Lab scale (L, a, b) and reported also as the a/b ratio, a widely adopted redness index in trade specifications and grading protocols. Standardisation relies on USDA/UC-Davis tomato soft standards and hitching to dedicated tomato tiles (USDA/UCD or BCR-400), ensuring inter-instrument agreement before routine measurement of pastes and purées.

Across large factory datasets collected at production (no storage effects), one commonly observes that redder pastes (higher a/b) are darker (lower L). This paper reviews why that inverse association is mechanistically and operationally expected, with emphasis on hot- vs cold-break decisions and evaporation regimes, and with explicit reference to Hunter Lab practice.

HUNTER LAB COLOUR IN TOMATO PRODUCTS

On the Hunter scale, L denotes lightness (0 = black; 100 = white), a the red–green axis (positive a = red), and b the yellow–blue axis (positive b = yellow). Tomato colour grading and “tomato scores” used in commerce are anchored in Hunter a and b (and their combinations), with prescribed instrument set-up, hitching, and sample handling. For pastes/purées, HunterLab recommends specific dilution (usually 12.5% Brix/optical-path controls to manage translucency so that L, a, b and derived metrics are repeatable.

PHYSICOCHEMICAL BASIS FOR AN INVERSE L–A/B RELATION

Lycopene—dominant tomato carotenoid—strongly absorbs 450–550 nm light. As lycopene concentration increases, redness (a and hence a/b) increases while overall reflectance decreases (so L falls). Empirically, lycopene correlates positively with a and with redness indices; in several datasets lightness L declines with increasing pigment concentration, yielding darker yet redder products. Although many correlation studies are on fresh tomatoes, the optical principle extends to concentrated systems (*ARIAS ET AL., 2000*).

Thermal processing adds two opposing influences: (i) beneficial concentration (more solids and more pigment per unit mass), which pushes a/b upward and L downward; versus (ii) degradation/isomerisation of lycopene and browning reactions that can suppress redness and further darken the matrix. The balance of these forces across industrial samples naturally generates a negative L–a/b slope (*BARREIRO ET AL., 1997; KOH ET AL., 2011*).

PROCESSING FACTORS

- Break system: cold vs hot

Cold-break ($\approx 60\text{--}70\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) applies lower initial heating; hot-break ($\approx 85\text{--}100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) rapidly inactivates PME/PG to secure viscosity. Multiple studies and industry sources converge: hot-break achieves higher viscosity but at the cost of browned/duller colour and greater nutrient losses; cold-break better preserves natural red colour and flavour. In colour terms, hot-break tends to lower L via browning and, when severe, can reduce a/b; cold-break tends to yield higher a/b at a given solids level (*GAO ET AL., 2021*). When lots span both regimes, hot-break batches cluster darker and (often) less red, whereas cold-break batches are brighter and redder. Mixed together, the cloud of points displays a negative L–a/b trend across production.

- Evaporation (vacuum vs atmospheric)

Concentration is the major colour-shaping unit operation. Vacuum evaporation lowers boiling temperature and residence time, improving lycopene retention and raising a/b relative to atmospheric boiling, which exhibits more pigment loss and browning for a given target Brix (*DEVSEREN ET AL., 2021; KOH ET AL., 2011*) similarly document carotenoid stability patterns across industrial processing. The colour consequence is intuitive: gentle vacuum concentration preserves red pigment (\uparrow a/b) and avoids excessive darkening; harsh atmospheric conditions do the opposite.

- Thermal browning and colour kinetics

Classic kinetic work on double-concentrated paste shows L, a, b, hue, and a/b follow temperature-time degradation during heating (70–100 °C), with measurable darkening (\downarrow L) and hue shift over time (*BARREIRO ET AL., 1997*). Non-enzymatic browning (Maillard reaction and sugar dehydration) yields melanoidins and markers such as HMF and furosine, both reported in heat-processed tomato products and used as browning indicators. Greater heat loads increase these compounds, coincident with lower L and, when pigment loss is significant, lower a/b.

MEASUREMENT PRACTICE ON THE HUNTER LAB SCALE

Robust interpretation requires method discipline: instrument hitching to USDA/UC-Davis or BCR-400 tomato tiles; adherence to USDA/AMS equations and HunterLab set-up notes; and tight control of sample presentation. Control dilution/optical path (e.g., standardised Brix for paste/purée) to manage translucency and scattering; fix cup geometry, port plate, and sample temperature. These factors influence absolute L more than the ratio, and inconsistent practice can steepen the apparent negative L–a/b slope across lots.

SYNTHESIS: WHY THE INVERSE RELATION IS EXPECTED

1) Optics of pigment loading: more lycopene increases a (and a/b) but decreases L due to lower reflectance (*ARIAS ET AL., 2000*).

2) Break choice: hot-break delivers viscosity but tends to brown/dull the colour; cold-break preserves redness. Across mixed operations, points align from dark/duller to bright/redder—i.e., a negative L–a/b gradient (*GAO ET AL., 2021*).

3) Evaporation severity: vacuum concentration mitigates pigment loss and darkening; atmospheric boiling does not. This contrast further drives separation along the inverse trend (*DEVSEREN ET AL., 2021; KOH ET AL., 2011*).

4) Browning kinetics: with increasing heat/time, L falls and hue shifts; if pigment also degrades, a/b falls—again strengthening the inverse relation (*BARREIRO ET AL., 1997*).

5) Metrology discipline: variability in dilution/path length and temperature disproportionately perturbs L; without strict standardisation, pooled datasets exhibit extra spread in L at given a/b, steepening the observed slope.

PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS (HOT VS COLD BREAK; EVAPORATION)

- If viscosity targets permit, prefer cold-break (or moderate hot-break) to preserve redness; when hot-break is required, minimise residence time and oxygen exposure (*GAO ET AL., 2021*).

- Use vacuum evaporation with the lowest feasible film temperature and short residence times to retain lycopene (\uparrow a/b) and limit darkening (\uparrow L relative to harsh boiling) (*DEVSEREN ET AL., 2021*).

- Standardise HunterLab protocols: hitch daily, fix sample depth/temperature, and measure at agreed dilution (for paste/purée). Apply USDA/AMS equations where colour scores are required.

CASE CONTEXT (PROCESSED TOMATO PASTE PRODUCTION DATASET, 2007–2025)

Within common tomato-paste ranges ($L = 18\text{--}26$, $a/b = 1.5\text{--}2.6$), an internal production dataset ($n = 47,114$ paired observations) shows Pearson $r \approx -0.264$ between L and a/b , with a simple linear fit $a/b = m \cdot L + c$ ($m = -0.05244$; $c = 3.55311$)—IC95% m $[-0.05417$; $-0.05071]$; IC95% c $[3.51227$; $3.59395]$; $R^2 = 0.0695$. These magnitudes are consistent with the mechanisms above: higher redness co-occurs with lower lightness; process choices (break/evaporation) and metrology explain much of the scatter around the trend. (Internal analysis; no storage effects considered.)

Fig. 1: Hunter L vs a/b (L 18–26; a/b 1,5–2,6).

Line: OLS adjustment with 95% confidence interval for the mean. $a/b = 3.55311 - 0.05244 \cdot L$; $r = -0.264$ (95% CI -0.272 to -0.255); $R^2 = 0.0695$; $n = 47,114$.

LIMITATIONS AND RESEARCH NEEDS

Many controlled studies isolate single variables (break temperature, evaporation temperature) and often use specific cultivars. Industrial data embed multiple simultaneous factors. Future work should combine pigment assays (HPLC lycopene), break/evaporation metadata, and strict HunterLab protocols in multivariate models to apportion contributions to L and a/b . Kinetic studies under actual vacuum-evaporator residence-time distributions would refine design targets.

CONCLUSIONS

The inverse association between Hunter L and a/b in tomato paste is the predictable outcome of pigment optics, thermal history (break and concentration), browning chemistry, and measurement practice. In operational terms, redder pastes (higher a/b) are typically darker (lower L)—especially when colour-preserving regimes (cold-break, vacuum evaporation) concentrate pigments without excessive thermal browning. Consistent HunterLab methodology is essential to separate genuine process effects from artefacts and to manage the L–a/b trade-off to specification.

OPERATIONAL ASSESSMENT OF A PROCESS SCORE (SIMÕES, 2021) AS A COMPLEMENT TO HUNTER L AND A/B

During the 2021 tomato season, the Process Score (PS) was calculated from 1,020 color data from aseptic filling lines. The preliminary findings suggested a strong correlation with the Hunter a value, but a moderate to poor correlation with the b and L values. To ascertain its validity and usefulness for evaluating the influence of the sterilizing procedure on tomato paste color characteristics, an extended research was conducted during the 2022 to 2025 tomato crops.

The PS integrates contributions from L, a, and b, weighted by the CIE x chromatic coordinate, and aims to simultaneously capture redness (a), yellowness (b), and darkness (L). CIE-x was calculated from Hunter Lab by:

$$CIE\ x = \frac{(a + 1.7 \cdot L)}{(5.64 \cdot L + a - 3.012 \cdot b)}$$

Buera's Browning Index (BI) is a relationship widely cited in the literature on color in food (Buera et al., 1986) and is defined by:

$$BI_{Buera} = \frac{CIE\ x - 0.31}{0.172} \cdot 100$$

$$PS_{Simoes} = \frac{T-W+V}{100} \text{ where: } T = 2 \cdot L^3 \cdot x; W = 2 \cdot b^3; V = a^3 \cdot CIE\ x$$

Methods — thresholds and classes

Operational thresholds: low L ≤ 23; high a/b ≥ 2.10; low a/b ≤ 1.90. Quadrants: A (low L, high a/b), B (low L, low a/b), C (high L, high a/b), D (high L, low a/b).

PS classes: <240 Out-of-Spec (Burnt), 240–270 Browning, 270–300 Standard (Deep red), >300 Standard (Bright red).

Results — summary by quadrant

- A (low L, high a/b): n = 1,302; PS ≈ 281 (IQR 34); L = 22.74; (a/b) ≈ 2.322. PS-class shares: 3.3% Burnt; 31.4% Browning; 42.5% Standard (Deep); 22.8% Standard (Bright).
- B (low L, low a/b): n = 1; PS ≈ 92; 100% Out-of-Spec (Burnt).

- C (high L, high a/b): n = 6,103; PS ≈ 303 (IQR 27); L = 23.68; (a/b) ≈ 2.286. PS-class shares: 0.2% Burnt; 6.9% Browning; 38.1% Standard (Deep); 54.8% Standard (Bright).
- D (high L, low a/b): n = 7; PS ≈ 99; 71.4% Out-of-Spec (Burnt).

Interpretation — In A, low L with high a/b does not typically indicate browning (two-thirds Standard). In B and D (low a/b), PS collapses and Out-of-Spec rises sharply, consistent with real darkening and red loss. PS therefore complements Hunter L and a/b for colour-preservation monitoring and product classification. The Process Score is relevant as a color preservation KPI and decision tool for sub-standard, especially when browning begins. It maintains L and a/b as base metrics and uses PS as a traffic light (consolidates the trend and reduces false positives of “darkened” when red is high).

A linear model fitted to all readings (PS as the response; L and a/b as predictors) explained 67.5% of the variance (R = 0.821; residual s.e. 13.55; n = 7,564):

$$PS = -919.806 + 27.651 L + 248.004 \cdot a/b$$

$$a/b_{\text{needed}} = \frac{PS + 919.806 - 27.651 \cdot L}{248.004}$$

Both partial effects were positive, indicating that, at constant a/b, increases in L elevate PS, and, at constant L, increases in a/b elevate PS. The resulting iso-PS boundaries on the L–a/b plane, show that low-L samples with sufficiently high a/b sit above the PS=270 “Standard” threshold, consistent with deep-red product rather than true browning; conversely, concurrent reductions in L and a/b locate below PS=270, i.e., sub-standard.

Fig. 2: Direct classification (PS=270 e PS=300)

Fig 3: L vs a/b with PS isochrones (270 and 300) and ±0.11 a/b bands

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APPENDIX — APPLIED COLORIMETRY: TOMATO PASTE COLOR (HUNTER LAB)

Contents of section 3.8 “APPLIED COLORIMETRY: TOMATO PASTE COLOR” (original text in English). Source: Campil – Essay on Light and Color, Carlos Paula Simões (1999), section 3.8 and subsections 3.8.1–3.8.5, including the modified COST90bis procedure and notes on the BCR/CRM 400 tile.

- Background

A European Community (EC) project (COST90bis) addressed colour measurement of foodstuffs. Tomato paste colour was judged of prime economic importance (≈ 600 MECU in 1986). State, academic and industrial labs collaborated in inter-comparison exercises. Two proposals emerged: (a) standardisation of tomato paste colour determination, and (b) a reference tile close to a good-quality tomato paste. A protocol was suggested (e.g., Brimelov; Hils). The Commission produced a certified reference tile (BCR/CRM 400) for calibration.

- Determination of Tomato Paste Colour

There is no single officially recognised European method, yet colour is a traded quality criterion. Reasons include: (1) raw tomato colour indicates maturity/flavour, and (2) paste colour is modified by processing and storage. Several procedures exist (notably in the USA) that convert tristimulus values to a USDA score; conversion factors often depend on instrument type. Common scoring systems are based on dilute pastes (≈ 8.5 % TSS), where translucency issues are more severe than at 12 % TSS (also used for Bostwick). US tiles are thus offset from a typical good paste at 12 % TSS. In line with COST90bis, improved accuracy is achieved using a reference tile close to typical paste colour (BCR/CRM 400). Preparation of ceramic reference tiles and a suggested standard method are described in BCR report EUR 13392 EN.

METHOD FOR THE COLOUR MEASUREMENT OF UNSALTED TOMATO PASTE/CONCENTRATE (MODIFIED COST90bis PROCEDURE)

A.1 Introduction

The technique calibrates a tristimulus colorimeter using a tomato paste colour reference tile typical of industry requirements. This reduces long-term instrument drift and improves reproducibility. The method avoids any glass plate between tiles and aperture.

A.2 Scope and Field of Application

Measurement of colour of unsalted tomato paste (concentrate) using a tomato paste colour reference tile.

A.3 Materials

A.3.1 Distilled water.

A.4 Apparatus

A.4.1 Tristimulus colorimeter; 50 mm nominal aperture recommended.

A.4.2 Standard black and white tiles at constant temperature (preferably 25 °C).

A.4.3 BCR Tomato Paste Colour Reference tile at constant temperature (preferably 25 °C).

A.4.4 Optically clear glass specimen cell, 62.5 mm diameter × 62.5 mm height; base thickness 2 mm; minimum sample depth 20 mm.

A.4.5 Empty, matte-black internal light shield (~100 mm internal diameter × 140 mm height).

A.4.6 Refractometer with sugar scale in % soluble solids.

A.4.7 Balance (capacity 500 g; readability 0.1 g).

A.4.8 Nylon muslin.

A.4.9 400 mL beakers.

Sampling and Samples

A.5.1 Preparation of %TSS: Cold-break — allow ≈50 g paste to 20 °C; express serum through nylon muslin; read refractometer within 5 s; repeat to constant reading. Hot-break — place ≈0.2 g directly on refractometer prism.

A.5.3 Test sample: net 300 g at 12.0 ± 0.1 % TSS. Approximate weight of undiluted paste W_p from $W_p = (12.3/\%TSS) \times 300$ g (12.3 rather than 12.0 accounts for total vs soluble solids). Add water at 20 °C in small increments, stirring to avoid lumps and AIR ENTRAPMENT. As mass approaches 300 g, check %TSS with ≈0.2 g on prism; adjust carefully to 12.0 ± 0.1 %. If over-diluted, DO NOT add more paste: discard and repeat.

Procedure

A.6.1 Use 45°/0° or 0°/45° geometry; Illuminant C; 2° Standard Observer; specular excluded; values expressed in Hunter L, a, b; referenced to a national Perfect White Diffuser.

A.6.2 Use an aperture of 50 mm nominal diameter (smaller diameters may introduce errors).

A.6.3 Zero with the black tile (clean, dust-free) according to the instrument manual.

A.6.4 Calibrate on the BCR Tomato Paste Reference Tile using certified values (without glass plate). Certified L, a, b are established at 25 °C; perform adjustments promptly to avoid warming.

A.6.5 Fill the specimen cell so the sample base is coplanar with the reference tile plane; ensure ≥20 mm depth; cover with light shield; read L, a, b quickly.

A.6.6 Zero and calibrate with the BCR tile at least every 2 hours.

A.6.7 Report results to 0.1 units.

SOME TOMATO PASTE COLOUR INDEXES (Illuminant C / 2° Standard Observer)

- Tc (Tomato Colour) = $(216 / 0.1L L) - (75 bL / 0.1L L)$
- TP (Tomato Paste) = $(-46.383 + 1.0211 aL + 10.670 bL - 0.4219 bL^2)$

Notes: The latter expression was introduced (1977) in USDA standards for tomato paste quality (maximum score 50/100). Separate relations are supplied for Hunter-Lab and Gardner instruments. An experimental correlation allows conversion of colour values between dilutions using Optical Residues ($OR1 < OR2$).

POSSIBLE CAUSES OF DISCREPANCIES WHEN MEASURING COLOUR IN TOMATO PASTE

- a) Different colorimeters (differences between Gardner and Hunter-Lab in L, a, b; a/b is less affected).
- b) Different dilutions (many packers use 12.0–12.5 % TSS; translucency varies with dilution).
- c) Thermochromism (sample and tiles at 20–25 °C; read quickly).
- d) Air entrapped and poor sample homogeneity.
- e) Insufficient sample depth (<20 mm).
- f) Dirty/damaged specimen glass cup (especially the bottom).
- g) Glass plate used during calibration (not approved by USDA or BCR; differences up to ≈10%).
- h) Support ring not used (ensures coplanarity of sample and tiles at the specimen port).
- i) Lightproof cover not used (with matte-black interior).